

Scientific Data Repository-related Policies: Colombia

Version 1

**International
Science Council**

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About the World Data System:

Founded in 2008, the World Data System (WDS) is an affiliated body of the International Science Council (ISC). Its mission is to enhance the capabilities, impact, and sustainability of its member repositories and data services by fostering trusted communities of scientific data repositories. The WDS also aims to strengthen the entire lifecycle of data management, ensuring that high-quality data supports first-class research output. Additionally, it advocates for accessible data along with transparent and reproducible science.

About the WDS series on Scientific Data Repository-related Policies:

The World Data System (WDS) Policy Series reviews country-specific policies related to the governance of scientific data repositories at the national level. Documenting these policies comprehensively is critical to fostering global collaborations and advancing science for the common good.

To this end, WDS is committed to maintaining and continually updating a list of national Open Science policies pertaining to data repositories. Additionally, WDS will host periodic webinars featuring experts from multiple countries to discuss their unique perspectives on Open Science Policies and how they impact data repositories. These sessions aim to inform researchers and policymakers on how to navigate international policy landscapes effectively.

In developing this Open Science Policy Series, WDS's goal is to create avenues for sharing knowledge and enhancing global scientific collaboration efforts. Ultimately, we hope this approach will promote transparency and ensure that science continues to work towards the common good by leveraging diverse international expertise. Note that the papers in this series will continually be updated with new and emerging information as it becomes available. The World Data System welcomes your input on these documents, including textual updates, references, policy suggestions, and link corrections, by emailing wds-ipo@utk.edu.

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Acronyms

BAC	Biblioteca Agropecuaria de Colombia
OA	Open Access
CONPES	Consejo Nacional de Política Económica y Social
ICDE	Infraestructura de Datos Espaciales
MinCiencias	Ministerio Nacional de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

Introduction

The World Data System (WDS) Policy Series reviews the specific policies of each country related to the governance of scientific data repositories at the national level. Documenting these policies comprehensively is essential for fostering global collaborations and advancing science for the common good. To this end, the WDS is committed to continuously maintaining and updating a list of national Open Science policies related to data repositories.

In this context, the present document describes the main guidelines, policies, and regulations that have been implemented in Colombia regarding data management. To that end, it first presents general data-related regulations, followed by specific guidelines for the management of data repositories and their corresponding description.

Scientific Data Repository-related Policies

Scientific data repository-related policies specific to Colombia include:

- Law 1712 of 2014

Defines open data as "todos aquellos datos primarios o sin procesar, que se encuentran en formatos estándar e interoperables que facilitan su acceso y reutilización, los cuales están bajo la custodia de las entidades públicas o privadas que cumplen con funciones públicas y que son puestos a disposición de cualquier ciudadano, de forma libre y sin restricciones, con el fin de que terceros puedan reutilizarlos y crear servicios derivados de los mismos." (all primary or raw data, which are in standard and interoperable formats that facilitate their access and reuse, and which are under the custody of public entities or private entities performing public functions, and made available to any citizen freely and without restrictions, so that third parties may reuse them and create derived services.) This Law became a reference point and thus laid the groundwork for subsequent regulations, aiming to guarantee access to information and promote the use of data for the development of the country through the adoption of standards that facilitate their use, analysis, and dissemination.

CONPES 3920 of 2018

- Statement on Transparency and Open Data

This was the first draft of a national policy focused on promoting the use of data, removing technological barriers, and encouraging data digitalization and openness, especially within the public sector. This CONPES establishes a legal framework aimed at classifying data, helping to restrict the dissemination of sensitive data, and encouraging the publication of data that contributes to national development. The document includes a diagnosis of the country's needs, particularly regarding human talent and infrastructure, in order to achieve successful implementation of the Policy.

- Resolution 0777 of 2022

This resolution adopts the National Open Science Policy 2022–2031, proposed by MinCiencias. The Policy aligns with the international context of Open Science promotion, becoming one of the first of its kind in Latin America.

It builds upon achievements made by various national institutions through programs or initiatives such as SiB Colombia, BAC, ICDE, and even the national open data portal. Its aim is to establish parameters for the exploitation, security, accessibility, and usability of data in the field of research. Furthermore, the Policy establishes strategies to increase human capital with the necessary capabilities and skills to manage and extract value from published data. It also includes incentives to encourage data dissemination and use.

It is important to note that this Policy stems from Resolution 0167 of 2019, which established the Guidelines for an Open Science Policy in Colombia, taking into account international standards and principles such as those of the OECD and UNESCO.

Likewise, at the level of various higher education institutions, there are regulations and guidelines for their institutional repositories. These establish criteria for the dissemination of documents, datasets, multimedia materials, among others, in accordance with different reproduction rights as determined by the authors or based on the characteristics of the item being deposited (UNAL, 2024).

At the national level, and in line with the International Open Data Charter, the Open Data Portal was made available—particularly for government entities—as a platform that provides datasets of public information in standard and interoperable formats, with the objective of being reused to create services and applications that are useful to the community.

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